

Welikia Soundscape Engine

Brendan Harmon · Jesse Allison · Hye Yeon Nam · Carlos Román · Joseph Brooks

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Summary

This project aims to reconstruct the historic soundscape of New York City before colonization. Reconstructing the historic soundscapes of New York City is challenging because the landscapes have been transformed and many species that were once present are no longer extant in the region. Even remnant patches such as old growth forest are acoustically distinct from their past as they no longer have the same species composition, abundance, and distribution. It is impossible to reconstruct these soundscapes from field recordings alone as key acoustic elements of the historic landscapes have been lost. Reconstructing these lost soundscapes from scratch by layering sounds from the predicted acoustic communities would sound synthetic and uncanny, missing the complex mosaic of background sounds – the acoustic interaction and interference between sounds in a real environment that gives a soundscape its depth and richness. With the Welikia Soundscape Engine, we demonstrate a novel method for reconstructing historic soundscapes by layering the sounds of the predicted acoustic community over soundbeds recorded in proxy landscapes. To reconstruct these lost soundscapes, we first collected field recordings at proxy sites, representing close analogs to historic landscapes. From these field recordings, we compiled soundbeds representing the background acoustics for a given landscape. Next we collected a database of biophonic, geophonic, and anthropophonic sounds including vocalizations by species predicted in the ecological reconstruction. We developed an object oriented ecoacoustic ontology in order to characterize the sounds of each soundtope – the sounds in a given patch within a greater landscape. Finally we designed a soundscape engine which uses the ontology to generate soundtopes by layering sounds in space and time over a soundbed. This research was funded by a grant from the New York Botanical Garden. The code was released under the MIT license and the dataset was released under the Creative Commons Zero public domain dedication.

Citing

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1 Introduction

1.1 Reconstructing Welikia

The Welikia Project by the New York Botanical Garden is a reconstruction of the historical ecology and natural geography of New York before colonization in 1609 [19, 10, 9]. The urban conservation team at the New York Botanical Garden used historic mapping and geospatial modeling to reconstruct the ecosystems of this region – Welikia, a name borrowed from the indigenous Lenape people. This research described the historic distribution and composition of ecosystems in the region. Building on their research, we are reconstructing the historic soundscapes of the region. Soundscapes – the sounds of a landscape as heard and interpreted by an audience [15] – are a key aspect of both ecology and our understanding of place. To reconstruct the historic soundscapes of New York, we developed the Welikia Soundscape Engine – a computational engine for generating soundscapes based on an ecoacoustic ontology. As a proof of concept, we used this engine to compose a reconstruction titled Biophilic Simulacra.

2 Concept

2.1 Ontology

An object oriented acoustic ontology serves as a framework for characterizing, categorizing, and synthesizing sound. Each sound is conceptualized as either a passive acoustic object with attributes or an active acoustic object with attributes and behaviors. In this ontology, sounds are categorized as ambient soundbeds, geophony, biophony, or anthropophony. Ambient sounds are diffuse, often unidentifiable environmental sounds representing the sonic background of an ecosystem. This sonic background is formed from a mosaic of attenuated and distorted geophonic and biophonic sounds [16]. It can include the rustle of leaves, insect choruses, and the indistinct calls of distant or occluded animals. For this soundscape reconstruction, ambient sounds are used as a soundbed, as an acoustic foundation for layering discrete, discernible sound objects. Geophony is sound generated by abiotic sources such as wind, thunder, rain, and flowing water, whereas biophony is sound generated by biotic sources such as animal communications including vocalizations, stridulations, and vibrations [16, 14]. Anthropophony is sound generated by human activity and for this reconstruction includes the sound of pre-colonial activities such as walking, canoeing, and controlled burns. Anthropogenic sounds that would not have been present before colonization are classified as noise – as unwanted acoustic signals – that should be cut or filtered from recordings. Noise in field recordings for soundbeds can include the sound of airplanes and automobiles.

2.2 Soundbeds

A soundbed, representing the ambient sounds of an ecosystem, is conceptualized as a passive acoustic object with a set of attributes that will be rendered as a diffuse field of sound. The attributes of a soundbed include the type of ecosystem, the potential ecological communities within the ecosystem, the time of day, the audio format, and geophonic activity. Time

is mapped as periods of acoustic activity – dawn, day, dusk, or night. For this reconstruction, ecosystems include forest, grasslands (Figure 1), tidal wetlands, freshwater wetlands, beaches, marine environments, and the cultural landscapes of the Lenape. Forest communities include oak-tulip tree forests, oak-hickory forests, pitch pine-scrub oak barrens, and coastal Atlantic white-cedar swamps. Tidal wetlands communities include salt marshes, salt pannes, and intertidal mudflats, while freshwater wetlands include wetland shrub swamps, red maple swamps and emergent marshes. Soundbeds can be built from field recordings collected in proxy landscapes. Field recordings should be taken in typical ecotopes within proxy landscapes that have been identified as the closest extant analog for historic landscapes. Day-long recordings can be taken with bioacoustic recorders for passive acoustic monitoring (Figure 2), while shorter ambisonic recordings which capture spheres of sound can be taken at key times of day such as dawn, midday, and dusk.

Figure 1: Soundbed – a meadow at dusk

Figure 2: Passive acoustic monitoring

2.3 Biophony

Biophonic sounds are conceptualized as discrete spatial sound objects with spatiotemporal attributes and behaviors. In this ontology, biophonic sounds are classified by their source taxa. For this reconstruction, biophonic sounds are classified as bird, mammal, or amphibian

calls (Figure 3) with each taxa having its own spatial and temporal behavior. Each biophonic sound object has attributes including the species' habitat preference and the time period of the recording – whether the recording was taken during dawn, day, dusk, or night. In our implementation, habitat preference maps directly to the types of ecosystems documented as soundbeds. The soundscape engine uses these attributes to layer biophonic sound objects over a soundbed in order to simulate the acoustic community of a given ecosystem. The engine uses behaviors such as position, motion, and frequency to situate these sound objects in space and time. Biophonic sounds can be collected from bioacoustic libraries such as xeno-canto [12] and the Macaulay library [11].

Figure 3: Biophony – a spring peeper chorus

2.4 Geophony

Geophonic sounds are conceptualized as sound objects for layering over soundbeds. In this reconstruction, they are categorized as weather and hydrological layers. The geophonic sounds implemented in this reconstruction include running water, wind, rain, and thunder (Figure 4). Geophonic sounds can be collected as field recordings or downloaded from open data repositories such as the Freesound library.

Figure 4: Geophony – rain and thunder

2.5 Anthropophony

Anthropophonic sounds, like biophony, are conceptualized as discrete spatial sound objects with spatiotemporal attributes and behaviors. The anthropophonic sounds implemented in this reconstruction include canoeing, controlled burns (Figure 5), and walking through forest, scrub, and beach. Anthropophonic sounds can be collected as field recordings or downloaded from open data repositories such as the Freesound library.

Figure 5: Anthropophony – a controlled burn

2.6 Engine

A soundscape engine mixes sound in space and time based on ecological rules and parameters to generate soundscapes. It can be used to reconstruct high fidelity, immersive soundscapes for historic landscapes by layering biophonic, geophonic, and anthropophonic sounds over soundbeds. To generate a soundscape, the engine queries a database of sounds, retrieves sounds, and assembles them in a composition. The engine uses an object oriented acoustic ontology to query, retrieve and construct sound objects based spatial, temporal, and ecological parameters. The soundscape is composed by layering and mixing selected samples of discrete sound objects over a diffuse soundbed object according to assembly rules. Sound objects are situated in and reverberate through space; each object is positioned within a spherical coordinate system centered on the listener – the audience. Active acoustic objects may have randomized behaviors defined by the ontology that unfold in time and space – a bear may walk across the soundscape, a vulture may circle overhead, or song birds may call and respond. The composition can represent a single soundtope (Figure 6) or a journey through the greater soundscape (Figure 7). While at any given moment the engine simulates a soundtope, the composition can explore geographies through the greater soundscape by transitioning through soundbeds. The soundscape engine can generate fixed media, i.e. recordings with stereophonic, binaural, or surround sound, or can be mixed live for performances.

Figure 6: Soundtope composition by layering acoustic objects

Figure 7: Journeying through a soundscape

3 Implementation

3.1 Fieldwork

Fieldwork for the *Welikia Soundscape Engine* was conducted through two intensive recording campaigns in the New York and New Jersey region during the fall of 2025 (Table 1). These field trips aimed to capture high-quality environmental audio representative of ecological communities corresponding to the historical ecosystems reconstructed by the Welikia Project [10, 9]. The team collected field recordings from proxy landscapes to build the soundbeds. Field recordings were taken in typical ecotopes within proxy landscapes that were identified as the closest extant analog for historic landscapes. Daylong recordings were taken with a bioacoustic recorder for passive acoustic monitoring in stereo format, while shorter ambisonic recordings which capture a sphere of sound were taken at dawn, midday, and dusk in select locations. The first phase of fieldwork was conducted from September 13-20, 2025 and the second phase was conducted from October 16-19, 2025. These time frames were selected to capture ecological activity in late summer and early autumn transitions, which influence species behavior, vegetation density, and acoustic characteristics.

The devices employed in fieldwork included the BAR-V2 stereo recorder, the Zoom H3-VR ambisonic recorder, and AudioMoth mono recorder. The stereo setup was used for extended diel cycle recordings to capture temporal variations in environmental soundscapes, while the ambisonic system enabled spatially detailed, immersive recordings of localized acoustic events for use in object-based rendering. AudioMoth recorders were primarily employed for documentation purposes, complementing the main raw dataset.

Microphone placement varied according to the characteristics of each ecosystem. The BAR-V2 recorder, equipped with mounting straps, was typically secured to tree trunks when available; in more open environments such as meadows or beaches, it was placed on stable, clean

Table 1: Field recordings

Location	Ecosystem	Community	Recordings
Sterling Forest, NY	Freshwater wetland	Shrub swamp	S · A
		Emergent marsh	S · A
		Riparian forest	S · A
	Forest	Oak-chestnut	S · A
		Oak-maple	S · A
New York Botanical Garden, NY	Forest	Oak-hickory	S · A
		Riparian hardwood	S · A
		Oak-beech-maple	S · A
	Freshwater wetland	Oak-maple hardwood	S · A
		Emergent marsh	S · A
Hunter Island, NY	Forest	Coastal oak-hickory	A
	Tidal wetland	Salt marsh	A
Ward Pound Ridge, NY	Forest	Oak-hickory	A
		Chestnut-oak	A
		Maple-oak	A
		Seepage	A
	Grassland	Tallgrass meadow	S · A
		Shrub thicket	S · A
	Freshwater wetland	Red maple swamp	M · S · A
Great Swamp, NJ	Freshwater wetland	Headwater streams	M · S · A
		Shrub swamp	A
	Forest	Emergent marsh	A
		Red maple swamp	A
Caumsett State Park, NY	Forest	Oak-beech	A
		Coastal oak-hickory	A
	Beach	Dune scrub	S · A
		Shore	S · A
	Tidal wetland	Salt marsh	S · A
		Maritime thicket	S · A
Ward's Point, NY	Freshwater wetland	Red maple pond	A
	Forest	Coastal oak-hickory	A
	Beach	Coastal thicket	S · A
	Tidal wetland	Salt marsh	S · A
Fire Island, NY	Beach	Maritime beach	S · A
		Salt panne	S · A
Long Island Pine Barrens, NY	Forest	Pitch pine-scrub oak barren	S · A

S: Diel cycle stereo · **M:** Diel cycle mono · **A:** Focal ambisonics

horizontal surfaces. The Zoom H3-VR recordings were either handheld or positioned at approximately head height using tree branches, rocks, or other natural supports. The ambisonic recorder was positioned usually near a zero-degree tilt to ensure accurate capture of the surrounding sound sphere and thus preserve spatial coherence.

3.2 Ontology

To ensure consistency, scalability, and interoperability between field recordings and the soundscape engine, the project implemented a domain-specific ontology that defines how audio data is categorized, labeled, and retrieved. This ontology functions as both a conceptual model of ecological soundscapes and a technical framework for organizing and querying audio assets within the system. This ontology enables the Max/MSP-based engine to: **1.** identify and retrieve recordings based on ecological criteria, **2.** combine multiple environmental layers dynamically, **3.** maintain semantic consistency across datasets and formats, **4.** and support user interaction and sound generation. The soundscape ontology is structured around a set of primary dimensions that describe each recording:

- 1. Ecosystem:** Defines the broad environmental category and classifies soundbeds as forest, tidal wetland, freshwater wetland, or beach
- 2. Time of Day:** Temporal classification of recordings as dawn, day, dusk, or night
- 3. Community:** Descriptive tags for habitat communities such as oak–hickory forest, shrub swamp, or salt marsh
- 4. Format:** Description of the recording type as mono, stereo, or ambisonic
- 5. Layers:** Optional layers for geophony and anthropophony

3.3 Objects

3.3.1 Soundbed Processing

All recordings underwent a post-processing workflow designed to produce ecologically coherent and robust soundbeds for integration into the libraries for the soundscape engine. The approach combined spectrographic analysis, critical listening, and manual editing with specific adaptations depending on the recording format.

For stereo diel cycle recordings, processing began with the identification of segments corresponding to representative times of day – dawn, day, dusk, and night. These segments were examined through spectrogram analysis to detect dominant acoustic features and locate potential sources of anthropogenic noise. Visual inspection of the spectrogram was particularly useful for identifying specific noise sources. Traffic noise which typically appears as continuous low-frequency energy below 300 Hz. Aircraft appear as evolving broadband traces. Car horns appear as narrow high-intensity bands. Human speech appears as formant structures with rhythmic modulation. These observations were validated through close listening, ensuring that selections from each recording preserved ecological coherence and perceptual continuity.

Modern anthropogenic sounds were then removed using two complementary strategies. Discrete events – such as passing vehicles, horns, or handling noise – were manually segmented and cut with crossfades applied to maintain smooth transitions. In contrast, persistent background noise – especially distant traffic – was mitigated using filtering techniques. A low-shelf filter with a cutoff around 300 Hz and a gain reduction of approximately –25 dB proved effective in reducing low-frequency noise while preserving relevant environmental content. This iterative process continued until a coherent soundbed of approximately 20 minutes was obtained. In cases where anthropogenic interference was pervasive, shorter durations were used to maintain quality.

To enable seamless playback, final versions of the soundbeds were edited into loopable audio files by extracting a segment from the end of the recording, placing it at the beginning, and applying a crossfade between the overlapping regions. Additionally, specific geophonic elements – such as water bodies or wind – were occasionally isolated and exported as separate files for use in other layers and libraries within the engine. For focal ambisonic recordings, a similar workflow was applied, although their shorter duration limited the extent of corrective editing. Selected ambisonic files were retained due to their spatial fidelity and their capacity to represent ecological detail. When anthropogenic noise could not be adequately removed through segmentation or filtering, recordings were discarded. Finally, mono recordings were used exclusively for documentation and archival purposes. The mono recordings captured with the AudioMoth were lower quality than the stereo and ambisonic recordings captured with the BAR-V2 and Zoom H3-VR devices. Therefore the mono recordings were not included in the final soundbed dataset or integrated into the soundscape engine.

3.3.2 Geophonic and Anthropophonic Layers

In addition to the field recordings obtained by our team, supplementary sound libraries were compiled for the geophonic and anthropophonic layers within the soundscape engine. These materials were sourced through an exhaustive search of publicly available sound databases, primarily the Freesound repository. Freesound is a collaborative, open-access platform that provides a large repository of user-contributed audio recordings [18, 4]. Most sounds are distributed under Creative Commons licenses, allowing reuse with varying conditions such as attribution requirements. All of these externally sourced sounds were properly attributed according to their respective Creative Commons license requirements in the metadata. Sound selection followed strict criteria to ensure compatibility with the ecological and perceptual goals of the project. Criteria included absence of unintended anthropogenic noise, acoustic representativeness of specific environmental processes, and compatibility with existing soundbeds in terms of texture, scale, and dynamics. The goal was to curate sounds that could be seamlessly integrated into the system without disrupting the ecological coherence of the soundbeds. Selected recordings underwent a simple, but consistent processing workflow. This included segmenting, filtering to remove residual noise and improve clarity, and application of fade-in and fade-out envelopes to ensure smooth triggering and looping behavior. To support flexible use within the soundscape engine, an additional classification based on duration was introduced. Short, discrete audio events can be triggered to function as randomized sound objects, while long recordings – such as sustained rain or flowing water – can function as continuous layers of sound. These layers can be blended into the soundbeds to enrich the overall soundscape environment.

3.3.3 Biophonic Layer

As part of the initial development and prototyping of the soundscape engine, a preliminary list of species was provided by the New York Botanical Garden team. This short list of forest species included raccoon, eastern gray squirrel, gray wolf, great horned owl, red-bellied woodpecker, red-eyed vireo, spring peepers, red spotted newt, and redback salamander. Based on this list, a collection of species-specific vocalizations was assembled using recordings sourced mainly from *xeno-canto*, an open-access, community-driven database specializing in species vocalizations from around the world. These recordings are typically shared under Creative Commons licenses, allowing reuse with attribution. All listed species, except for the amphibians, were represented in the resulting dataset. Although visual documentation for these amphibian species is widely available, reliable recordings of vocalizations are scarce or nonexistent, limiting their inclusion in the biophonic layer.

Recordings from *xeno-canto* were initially selected based on their quality ranking on the platform. The selection process presented significant challenges. Many recordings available in public databases are captured in urban or semi-urban environments that often have substantial anthropogenic noise or in complex ecological settings where multiple species overlap acoustically. As a result, an exhaustive search and evaluation process was required. The primary objective was to identify recordings in which the target species' vocalizations were as isolated and clearly distinguishable as possible, minimizing interference from other biological or anthropogenic sources. Species recordings were also filtered by geographic location. Using *xeno-canto*'s location-based search, recordings from New York State were prioritized, followed by, when necessary, recordings from the broader eastern region of the United States. Selected recordings underwent an editing workflow to enhance clarity and usability within the soundscape engine including segmentation of relevant vocalizations, crossfading to ensure smooth integration, and band-pass filtering to isolate frequency regions associated with the target species. In addition to duration-based classification as short or long samples, an additional tag was introduced to describe the type of vocalization, such as call or song, to enable behavioral modeling within the engine.

3.4 Engine

The Biomass Speculator, our engine for synthesizing soundscapes, is designed around the organization of objects in a scene. Objects have properties including placement, loudness, and directionality, typically in relation to a listener, as well as content – the plants, animals, and environments that they represent. These objects fall into two general categories – source-objects and sound-objects.

There is a linguistic and conceptual fuzziness between the thing that makes a sound and the sound itself. For instance a wolf – a source-object – may create a howl while a call and response – a sound-object – might consist of a pair of wolves howling to each other in the distance. The howl is a sound-object and might have traits like loudness, location, and directionality. The wolf could be considered a source-object and have a location, direction, and the motivation to make the howl of a certain variety, loudness and in a certain direction. These two objects, the source-object and the resultant sound-object are both worthwhile concepts in constructing a soundscape. A sound-object can be built from smaller parts, but must have

a self-consistency, a cohesiveness that binds the object as an entity sufficient within itself. In the call and response howling situation, one might consider it as a construction of two individual wolves, each with their own position, location in relation to surroundings, direction, and motivation for making a howl of a certain variety. Classifying one howl as a call and one as a response reflects the individual nature of the sound-objects and the relationship between the two. Alternately, taken as a whole, the sound-object of wolf call and response howls is much different. It would have a size and scope – i.e. a distance between sounds and position relative to the listener. Differentiated from the concept of the source-object, this sound-object represents the sound itself with all of its constituent properties. The environment and location of the two wolves is encoded into the resultant audio recording and cannot easily be manipulated.

A mono source recording captures an acoustic scene from a single viewpoint, with very little directionality information, although it contains some depth information. Because of this, the environmental sound in a mono recording is confusing when replayed – the entire scene seems to emanate from a specific location, or more accurately, from all directions. For soundscape reconstruction, the best usage of mono recordings is to isolate near field sound sources from the environmental background, so that these source-objects can be realistically positioned in an acoustic scene of our own creation without environmental confusion. On the other hand, stereo source recording captures a viable, if incomplete, acoustic scene retaining left, right, and depth information. Depending on the listening setup, this would allow us to stretch the acoustic scene across two or more speakers and retain a viable image – like a portal or window into the place in the recording. Ambisonic recordings are a useful combination of the two, offering a single viewpoint into the acoustic scene, but capturing sound in all directions. Ambisonics retain left and right, up and down, and front and back information. The acoustic scene can later be rotated, expanded and contracted, focused in a direction, and then rendered for any collection of speakers. The scene can be rendered in stereo, offering a window into the sound image, or in binaural or multichannel audio for spatial immersion inside of the sound image.

Our process for reconstructing soundscapes uses an object oriented ontology, is grounded in this relationship between source and sound, and is constrained by audio recording techniques. Ambisonic and stereo source recordings function well as base layers representing the ambient environment. As long as the environmental sounds are low or complimentary, additional geophonic, anthropophonic, or biophonic recordings can be layered over the environment. If there are conflicting environmental sounds, then there is a risk of confusion. With well prepared samples, however, this risk can be minimized. Ambisonic and stereo source recordings of environmental sound can be manipulated – repositioned and reoriented within 3-dimensional space – and then layered together into a realistic scene.

Because biophonic and anthropophonic layers contain behavioral information they are challenging to combine with environmental scenes. Often they can be layered successfully if their background noises do not conflict. They, however, can not be altered to represent different behaviors by their source-objects. Instead the engine approaches them as actors, modeling behaviors that generate sounds. This requires careful preparation of a sufficient number of sound-object files to represent the variety of behaviors being modeled. In combination with calculated positioning, event timing, time-stretch, pitch-shifting, and other effects, actors can be used to synthesize greater sound-objects for layering into environmental scenes.

4 Products

4.1 Recordings

This bioacoustic dataset documents soundscapes in the New York and New Jersey region for the Welikia Project. Field recordings were collected in the fall of 2025 to capture environmental audio for a reconstruction of the historic soundscapes of the region. This dataset includes 282 raw audio recordings from 9 field locations in ambisonic, stereophonic, or monophonic format. The following table summarizes the raw recordings, organized by recording location and format (Table 2).

Dataset

Brendan Harmon, Jesse Allison, Hye Yeon Nam, Carlos Román, and Joseph Brooks. *Welikia Soundscape Recordings*. Version 1.0.0. License: Creative Commons Zero. Louisiana State University, 2026. DOI: 10.82176/landarch_data.1

Table 2: Raw recordings

Location	Ambix	Mono	Stereo
Sterling Forest State Park, NY	12	0	38
New York Botanical Garden, NY	4	4	17
Hunter Island, NY	8	0	0
Ward Pound Ridge Reservation, NY	21	8	38
Great Swamp National Wildlife Refuge, NJ	3	0	0
Caumsett State Historic Park Preserve, NY	15	5	17
Ward's Point, NY	4	0	23
Fire Island National Seashore, NY	5	0	38
Long Island State Pine Barrens Preserve, NY	4	0	18
	76	17	189
Total			282

4.2 Library

This acoustic dataset contains soundbeds, biophonic sounds, geophonic sounds, and anthropophonic sounds for reconstructing the historic soundscapes of New York.

Dataset

Brendan Harmon, Jesse Allison, Hye Yeon Nam, Carlos Román, and Joseph Brooks. *Welikia Soundscape Library*. Version 1.0.0. License: Creative Commons Zero. Zenodo, 2026. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18819403

4.3 Software

The Biomass Speculator software engine was developed in Max [13] to synthesize soundscapes for the Welikia project. It is designed as a Max package and can be installed simply by placing it in the Max package folder. It uses the SPAT library from IRCAM [17, 8] to handle localization for spatial audio rendering in ambisonic and binaural formats. SPAT can be installed using the Max package manager. Within each module, 3rd order ambisonics are used as a good balance between spatial information and processing power. The results are then rendered in 1st order ambix format for export.

The base collection of objects is separated into ecosystems – including environments and actors – and components consisting of collections of files, spatialization tools, utilities including random processes modeling behavioral patterns, and other tools for building more viable actors (Table 3). The toolset is in beta development phase and was used as a proof of concept to create a soundscape composition titled Biophilic Simulacra. Prototype actors were developed for certain basic behaviors of wolves, peepers, and owls.

Usage of the library could take many forms, but would typically involve choosing a soundbed, then layering in geophonic, anthropophonic, and biophonic sounds, and finally creating actors that model more complex behaviors. After an actor is instantiated, its behavior is defined and then it is released and layered back into the soundscape composition. Positioning parameters for any of these sound-objects can be preset or applied in real time to create a final, realistic scene. The output is listened to, rendered down to 1st order ambisonics, and saved in ambix format. Environments can be set as a base environmental site recording in place of a soundbed. Alternatively, geophonic sound files with limited environmental noise that can be effectively layered over the soundbed. The `bio.soundbed` module accesses a sound-database with prepared samples representing a variety of soundbeds at various times of day. The object reads a prepared JSON file with metadata for each recording including environmental classification, time of day, and tags identifying the content. These can be used to navigate and select the desired soundbed. It can also be used to navigate geophony and anthropophony recordings for layering over the soundbed.

Actors are more complex, combining behaviors that access and manipulate sets of recordings along with parameters of the source-object to create a final sound-object. An actors behavior may be modeled including the location, timing, and characteristics of any created sound-objects. The `bio.collection` module may be used to access the sound database which has samples representing a variety of behaviors for the selected biophony. Each behavior may have sets of samples that can be assigned or randomly chosen. Depending upon the behavior, effects may be applied to further represent the individuality of the source-objects' motivations. For instance, a frog peep may vary in duration and fluctuate in pitch with each repetition.

The Biomass Speculator is still under development, but offers a framework on which to build further biophilic actors, model behaviors, and integrate with the Welikia database to automatically render viable ecoacoustic scenes. Future development plans include working with researchers to create actors, expand the types of behaviors modeled, and improve sound database navigation. Future development could also synchronize the render pipeline and output formats for other intended uses.

Table 3: Biomass Speculator List of Objects & Modules

Type	Object	Usage	Status
Environments	bio.soundbeds	Navigation and playback of sound database	C
Actors	bio.actor	Model for biophilia with behaviors	P
	bio.body	Creates a representative body displayed in bio.viz	C
Collections	bio.collection	Navigation and playback of sets of sounds	C
	bio.navigator	Navigation of sound database to create sets	F
	bio.files	JSON representation of audio files	F
	bio.set	JSON representation for curation	F
Utilities	bio.recorder	Recording to ambix format	C
	bio.preset	Handling presets in developed modules	F
	bio.randomLocation	Behavioral modeling	C
	bio.meander	Behavioral modeling	C
	bio.travel	Behavioral modeling of movement	P
	bio.trajectory	Behavioral modeling of movement paths	F
Spatialization	bio.location	Positioning of sound-object	C
	bio.ambix	Transcoding 3rd to 1st order ambisonics in ambix	C
	bio.binaural	Encoding into binaural rendering	F
	bio.viz	Visualizer for objects with a bio.body	P

C: Current · **P:** Preliminary · **F:** Future

Repository

[Software] Jesse Allison, *Biomass Speculator* version 0.1.0, 2026. Louisiana State University.
vcs: <https://github.com/jtallison/biomass-speculator>

4.4 Soundscapes

Biophilic simulacra is a sonic artwork that was created as a proof of concept to demonstrate our process for soundscape synthesis. It uses the soundtope and sound object conceptualization described above to synthesize outputs of the Biomass Speculator as it was being formalized. The composition (Table 4) was created using a combination of audio source types and preparations. These preparations included various plugins and other audio effects in Twisted Wave and Max 9 using constructions in the Biomass Speculator. These processes delivered sound objects that were then assembled with soundbeds in Reaper taking advantage of the Feidler audio ATMOS renderer, the IEM Ambix plugins, binaural plugins, and the Ambisonic Toolkit. The soundbeds were primarily ambix recordings with a few stereo recordings to compare effectiveness and transparency when moving from stereo to multichannel rendering. The other sound objects were an intentional mixture of mono, stereo, binaural, and ambisonic files to expose and illuminate issues with integrating different types of spatial audio into a cohesive output.

The composition begins by fading into an oak forest, immersing the listener in an environmental source recording. A stereo source recording of wolf sounds captured with a close mic is layered on top of the forest soundbed. This transitions into a bio-simulation of nearby wolf

noises and then into near and far wolf calls that are ambisonically positioned. These were our first experiments with synthesized biophony. They were used to explore the positioning of nearby animals and translation of stereo to ambisonic sound files. Problems arose in modeling realistic behavioral movements of the wolves including the presence or absence of padding feet or rustling bushes to match the artificial motion of the wolves. Movement initially induced the feeling of turning ones' head and rotating the acoustic scene. Once the location of the wolves was established for wolf calls, they were successfully integrated into the environment. The end of this section concludes with airplane noise captured in the original soundbed bringing us out of the pristine, undisturbed nature of the soundscape.

The brook section starts with a sharp cut from the airplane anthropophony to a soundbed for an oak-hickory forest with a brook. This section explores the effective layering of geophony and integration of biophonic stereo source recordings. Owl biophony from a stereo site recording was encoded into ambix format, successfully rotated, placed in the distance, and positioned at tree height. A stereo source recording of rain was encoded into ambix and gradually overtakes the sound of the brook as the prominent water feature. The rain recording felt closer, with the sound of nearby droplets hitting plants evoking the feeling of being enveloped by rain. The sound of thunder rolled in the distance twice as the rain slowly ended and the sound of the swamp emerged. This section, although rapidly moving from one soundtope to another, is quite effective at placing the listener in the desired environment.

The emergent swamp soundbeds recorded in ambix are teeming with the sounds of insects, birds, and amphibians. This section experimented with techniques for translating between biophonic stereo and ambix source recordings, mono source recordings position ambisonically, and speculative sound recordings created in the biomass speculator. It begins with a daytime emergent swamp soundbed absent of frogs. A single peeper is introduced with a mono recording encoded and positioned in ambisonics. This peep is responded to by another peeper generated and positioned with the biomass speculator. The two interact with each other briefly. At this point the source recording rapidly fades into a soundbed of the swamp at dusk with many peepers in the ambisonic recording. A biomass speculator reconstruction of the peepers at night was generated and the layered over the soundbed. Almost imperceptibly the soundbed drops out until we are only listening to the reconstructed peepers without environmental sounds. It ends on a sudden chirp and the final section fades in. There are a few final chirps created in the biomass speculator that are layered in to finish the transition.

The final section explores the progression of soundtopes over the course of a day – exploiting the natural perception of the time of day that is encoded in source recordings. It begins in an oak-hickory forest soundbed recorded at dawn with insect and bird calls setting the scene. After 30 seconds, it quickly fades to a mid-day recording with more active biophony including squirrels, birds, and a little wind that effectively indicate the progression of time. This is followed by a brief transition to a dusk recording that lowers the environmental background noise and includes a different set of insect sounds to communicate the peacefulness of evening. Finally, stereo owl recordings are brought back, positioned through ambisonics, and layered onto the soundbed. These gradually space apart and slow down through increasingly dramatic time stretching as the soundbed fades out, leaving the listener with the uncanny perception that the owl is not a part of the scene, but rather a distinctly unreal, digital entity.

Table 4: Biophilic Simulacra Timeline

Section	Time	Sounds	Notes	File
Forest	0'00"	Oak forest	Fade in on an ambisonic recording of an oak forest.	A
	0'32"	Canis Lupis	Mixing biosimulation with field recording. Recreated wolf sounds in 1st order ambisonics.	R
	0'38"	Canis Lupis	Stereo sound file of nearby wolf snuffling. Encoded into Ambix format and automatically positioned.	S
	1'28"	Airplane	Human noise intrudes. The noise of airplane grows in loudness until a hard cut into the brook section.	A
Water	1'36"	Brook	A sharp cut to the oak-hickory forest with a brook during daytime.	A
	1'48"	Bubo virginianus	Three stereo great horned owl recordings are encoded into ambix format, positioned in treetops, and played.	S
	2'08"	Rain	Rain fades in, simulating interaction with the foliage and running brook.	S
	2'26"	Thunder	The brook crossfades out as rain and thunder crossfade in and take over. Stereo encoded into ambix.	S
Swamp	2'56"	Red maple swamp	Rain fades out as a swamp fades in. Ambix recording of swamp including insects.	A
	3'05"	Pseudacris crucifer	Mono biophony with spring peeper encoded and positioned ambisonically.	M
	3'10"	Pseudacris crucifer	Transition between source and reconstructed recordings. Peeper mixed in dialogue with a reconstructed peeper. By 3'14 this peeper is alone.	R
	3'23"	Pseudacris crucifer	Stereo peeper is encoded into ambix and presented alone.	S
	3'42"	Pseudacris crucifer	A chorus of peepers. Crossfade to stereo field recording encoded to ambix. The swamp recording is now over.	S
	3'55" 4'11"	Pseudacris crucifer Pseudacris crucifer	Xrossfade to reconstructed peeper sounds alone. Peeps at 4'12", 16", 20", 23", & 26".	R R
Time	4'14"	Dawn	Oak-hickory forest at dawn with woodpecker.	A
	4'46"	Mid-day	Oak-maple forest during the day.	A
	5'23"	Dusk	Oak-hickory forest at dusk.	A
	5'29"	Bubo virginianus	Great horned owl at 5'29", 39", and 49". The last sample is time-stretched until it sounds unnaturally digital. Stereo recording encoded into ambix and localized.	S

M: Mono · **S:** Stereo · **A:** Ambisonic · **R:** Ambisonic reconstructions

Streaming

Jesse Allison. *Biophilic Simulacra*. 2026. url: <https://on.soundcloud.com/TUuWZhKvbV1G1i3Vwf>

Archive

Jesse Allison. *Biophilic Simulacra*. Version 31Jan2026. Zenodo, Jan. 2026. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20389278

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